

1 **Biochar amendment, plant diversity and vigor: Assessing yield-diversity trade-offs in a**
2 **Mediterranean biodiverse pasture**

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19 **Abstract**

20 In intensive silage and pasture production systems, yield-increasing measures - e.g. inorganic
21 fertilization, re-sowing with a few productive species, frequent soil tillage, irrigation, and liming -
22 are invasive and can have negative impacts on the survival of native species, compromising
23 composition and diversity of local vegetation. Biochar has potential to increase crop yields, while
24 benefiting soil ecosystem services and functions, but the effects of its application to soil on plant
25 community composition and diversity in grasslands are not known.

26 We studied the extent of trade-offs between biochar-induced biomass increase and plant
27 community composition, diversity, and vigor of a sown biodiverse pasture in drought-affected
28 acidic granitic soil. Mixed-effects and multivariate abundance models were used to analyze
29 species- and community- level responses.

30 Biochar application caused significant soil-niche expansion for grasses and legumes from the
31 seed mixture, increasing their total and relative biomass by 110% and 59%, respectively. In the
32 biochar treatment, a moderate competitive exclusion from seed mixture species towards native
33 forbs was observed but never reached a point of competitive displacement, thus, allowing for a
34 competitive coexistence. No significant reductions in species' biomass, but moderately reduced
35 abundances, led to 50-97% improved vigor for sown species and 53-153% for native species in
36 biochar treatment, pointing at the process of interspecific thinning. There was no competitive
37 exclusion between grasses and legumes from the seed mixture in biochar treatment, as is usually
38 observed under fertilizer-based biomass increases. Thus, their niche partitioning did not appear
39 compromised. Species richness, count-based and biomass-based Shannon, Gini-Simpson, and
40 evenness indices, as well as Renyi diversity profiles, did not significantly differ between control

41 and biochar treatment. Multivariate abundance models captured a slight community shift in
42 biochar-amended soil, but without clear distinction by indicator species. Moderate reductions of
43 native forbs abundances, and high increases in biomass and abundances of seed mixture species
44 in biochar treatment allowed for a competitive co-existence between species of high agronomic
45 value and native species important for biodiversity and habitat function. This demonstrates that
46 biochar addition to soil has the potential to maintain biodiverse pastures while improving fodder
47 productivity and quality in acidic-granitic soils of Mediterranean climate.

48 **Keywords:** Mediterranean grasslands, biodiversity loss, competitive exclusion, competitive co-
49 existence, competitive displacement, niche partitioning, drought, acidic soils, hard-setting soils,
50 granitic soils, sustainable grassland management, experimental agroecology

51 **1. Introduction**

52 Grasslands are among the most widespread semi-natural ecosystems ([Hejman et al 2013](#)),
53 providing numerous provisioning, regulating, cultural and supporting ecosystem services (ESs).
54 They are the dominant agroecosystems used for livestock farming, while at the same time
55 harboring a high plant and animal diversity, and impacting on many ecosystem functions
56 ([Petermann and Buzhdygan 2021](#)). In Europe, permanent grasslands cover around 32% of
57 agricultural land ([Eurostat 2023](#)). Due to intensification of grassland management after the
58 Second World War, many European countries converted semi-natural grasslands into high
59 productivity pastures and silage production systems that require large input of inorganic
60 fertilizers, frequent soil tillage, and resowing with only a few species of grasses and legumes
61 ([Leuschner et al. 2024](#), [Plantureux et al. 2005](#), [Rochon et al. 2004](#)). This has led to worldwide
62 loss of natural grassland habitats and associated biodiversity-mediated ESs, and still causes

63 disappearance of grassland communities and habitats for many insects, especially pollinators, soil
64 fauna and birds ([Klein et al. 2020](#), [Orford et al. 2016](#), [Tsiafouli et al. 2015](#), [Douglas et al. 2023](#)).

65 In intensive grassland management, the most common yield-increasing measures include
66 inorganic fertilization (particularly N-based), soil liming, frequent tillage with resowing, and
67 amelioration and irrigation in case of gleyic and drought-affected soils, respectively. N
68 fertilization leads to increases in aboveground biomass, but reduces plant diversity ([Kidd et al.](#)
69 [2017](#), [Mauchamp et al. 2016](#), [Pallett et al. 2016](#), [Bai et al. 2009](#), [Humbert et al. 2016](#)), thus
70 compromising the community composition and diversity of grasslands. This has knock-on effects
71 on ecosystem functioning and the food webs of grasslands, as few dominant species (mostly
72 grasses) outcompete most autochthonous plants ([Pallett et al. 2016](#), [Kidd et al. 2017](#)) that serve as
73 a habitat to many animals, especially insects. In addition, eutrophication related to overuse of N
74 and P fertilizers negatively affects soil and freshwater biota, but also the whole landscape by
75 causing ground-water nitrate and phosphate contamination ([Bijay-Singh and Craswell 2021](#),
76 [Srivastav et al 2024](#)). Liming acidic soils typically increases their agronomic productivity,
77 especially in acidic oligotrophic grasslands. Liming can lead to species displacement, in which
78 native acidophilic species are replaced by more generalist species that have higher fodder quality
79 ([Spiegelberger et al. 2010](#), [Mosquera-Losada et al. 2009](#)). For this reason, various EU countries
80 discourage the liming of acidic oligotrophic grasslands, considering their special status under the
81 Natura 2000 framework EU Habitats Directive ([Council Directive 92/43/EEC](#)). Irrigation is the
82 most common solution to drought in grasslands, but is becoming increasingly less sustainable in
83 view of current climate-change and socio-economic scenarios, and can also lead to displacement
84 of drought resistant autochthonous grassland species ([Cramer et al. 2018](#); [Müller et al. 2016](#)). All
85 of these methods of improving grassland productivity might have positive agronomic results,

86 however, they work via chronic (i.e. invasive) resource addition, with the consequence of causing
87 a shock to the community stability and ecosystem functioning.

88 Currently, more sustainable development frameworks are being implemented in the European
89 Union aiming to put extensification of grasslands into practice to reverse biodiversity loss, i.e.
90 EU Biodiversity initiative 2030 ([European Commission 2020](#)), EU Pollinators initiative
91 ([European Commission 2021](#)) and EU's Common Agricultural Policy ([European Parliament &
92 Council of the European Union 2021](#)). However, extensification comes with a trade-off between
93 biomass yield and diversity, as mentioned before. Extensive biodiverse grasslands may be
94 suitable for organic farming; however, large farming units may still feel challenged to maintain
95 economic competitiveness, thus, in this case, minimizing trade-offs between productivity and
96 diversity becomes more complicated.

97 In Mediterranean countries, highly intensified forage and silage production based on grasslands is
98 not as widespread as it is in Northern and Central Europe, due to unfavorable soil and climate
99 conditions, especially vegetation stagnation during the long summer periods, caused by high
100 temperatures and minimal rainfall. In the Iberian Peninsula, grasslands utilized for silage or
101 pasture production are often established from diverse legume-grass seed mixtures, aimed at
102 agronomic productivity, while benefiting biodiversity and ESs ([Teixeira et al. 2015](#), [Hernández-
103 Esteban et al. 2019](#)). In Portugal, over 50,000 ha of grasslands are sown with biodiverse sown
104 pastures rich in legumes (SBPPRL), a.k.a. sown biodiverse pastures (SBPs), whose practice
105 started in the 1960s and encompasses legume-grass seed mixtures containing up to 20 plant
106 species ([Teixeira et al. 2015](#)).

107 Biochar, i.e. a solid, multi-functional, porous carbonaceous product of agricultural biomass
108 pyrolysis (Bilias et al. 2024), is known to increase plant growth, due to positive effects on both
109 physicochemical, and biological soil properties (Jeffery et al., 2024). Its porous structure and
110 large surface area enhance the soil's 'sponge' function for water infiltration, retention and
111 exchange (Edeh et al. 2020; Gholamahmadi et al. 2023), and its ash, rich in macro- and micro-
112 nutrients, can have a direct positive effect on soil nutrient status and pH, leading to increased
113 crop yield (Jeffery et al. 2017) while potentially providing benefits to other soil-based ecosystem
114 services (Gholamahmadi et al. 2023; Giu et al. 2025). However, studies regarding these aspects
115 in grassland communities are scarce, where there are, to our knowledge, presently no published
116 field studies about biochar effects on whole plant community composition, diversity, and vigor.
117 Controlled pot experiments are limited to soil heavy metal remediation with biochar and its effect
118 on plant community features (Yuan et al. 2024; Wang et al. 2024a; Meng et al. 2023), and on
119 saline community restoration (Wang et al. 2024b). An exception is a grassland community-level
120 research study conducted by van de Voorde et al. (2014) in a Dutch nature restoration area, in
121 which they found an increase in legume productivity in biochar-amended soil. However,
122 community diversity responses were not analyzed. Biochar increased aboveground biomass while
123 shifting the community structure at the functional group level in favor of legumes, relative to
124 grasses and forbs, in a lysimeter experiment using the SBP seed mixture on a degraded vineyard
125 soil (Gholamahmadi et al. 2025).

126 In our previous field research, we found that when applied to a hard-setting pasture soil in a
127 drought-affected area, biochar increased total aboveground dry biomass production of SBP from
128 6 to 9 t/ha, as well as that of total grasses and legumes, while not significantly reducing total
129 biomass of native forb species (Jelinčić et al. 2025). In a similar study, we found that biochar

130 treatment at the same concentration increased total biomass from 5.0 to 7.3 t/ha (Jongen et al.
131 2024). However, how biochar addition to soil can affect community composition and diversity of
132 SBP remains largely unknown. Whether this increase in aboveground productivity comes with
133 negative trade-offs against those two (as is documented when measures of chronic resource
134 addition are used in grasslands, i.e. N fertilizers, liming, and irrigation) needs to be investigated.
135 In the present study, we hypothesized that: 1) the increase in SBP aboveground productivity in
136 biochar-amended hard-setting soil in a drought affected area does not come with negative trade-
137 offs with community composition and diversity; 2) biochar addition to soil benefits establishment
138 and increases biomass, abundance, and vigor of seed mixture species, especially those of
139 legumes.

140 **2. Materials and methods**

141 **2.1 Study site, soil and biochar characterization**

142 The study was performed in central Portugal, at the Quinta de França farm (40°16'25.89"N,
143 7°25'34.35"W), managed by Terraprima (www.terraprima.pt). The area is within the
144 Mediterranean phytogeographic region and is characterized by hot and dry summers and mild and
145 wet winters (Csa in Köppen classification). Long-term annual average rainfall equals 858±283
146 mm, with approximately 90% occurring between Oct 1st – May 31st (<https://snirh.apambiente.pt/>,
147 mean of eight meteorological stations situated within 20 km of the field site). Mean temperatures
148 of the coldest (January) and warmest (July) months are 8°C and 27°C, respectively
149 (<https://weatherandclimate.com/portugal/castelo-branco/carria>). The soil type is a dystric
150 Cambisol (IUSS 2014) in the WRB system, Xerochrept (USDA 2014) in the Soil Taxonomy
151 system or Pgm type in the Portuguese classification (SROA 1970). The soil texture is sandy-

152 loam. The soil is developed over granite bedrock and exhibits a hard-setting behavior (Daniells
153 2012). Biochar used in this study was acquired from NovoCarbo[®], derived from *Pinus sylvestris*
154 woodchips pyrolyzed at 700°C. Its main physico-chemical characteristics are listed in Appendix
155 S1: Table S1.

156 The site is a sown biodiverse permanent pasture rich in legumes. The sown seed mixture contains
157 different cultivars of each species, in relative proportions that are tailored to meet specific
158 production areas as well as soil and climate characteristics (detailed description of the concept in
159 Teixeira et al. 2015). These mixtures are used for establishing permanent pastures, in which the
160 plant community is left mostly ungrazed during the first season after seeding, allowing all species
161 to flower and reproduce to increase the pasture's seedbank for the following seasons. Even
162 though species in the seed mixture are mostly annuals, the pastures are considered permanent, as
163 each season the species re-seed themselves from the seed bank. Autochthonous grassland species
164 are left to grow freely along with the species sown from the seed mixture and are not weeded out
165 or managed in any way. The exception is in the case of shrub encroachment, but shrubs are
166 partially outcompeted because they are less adapted to the higher grazing pressures allowed by
167 SBPs. Thus, SBP's are species-rich and support plant, animal, and microbial biodiversity, while
168 having highly improved agronomic productivity compared to semi-natural extensive pastures.
169 This benefits many ecosystem services, such as improved soil organic matter accumulation
170 (Teixeira et al. 2011), and increased water infiltration and reduced run-off (de Oliveira Ramos
171 2011). N nutrition in SBP solely relies on atmospheric N fixed by legumes, whose seeds are
172 inoculated with *Rhizobia* sp. before sowing to maximize N₂ fixation. SBPs are typically fertilized
173 with P, as efficiency of N fixation depends on P availability (Hernández et al. 2009) and
174 Portuguese soils are usually P deficient. This form of grassland management is utilized by some

175 big farms in Portugal, benefiting biodiversity and ecosystem services, while providing economic
176 amounts of biomass yield. Today, the use of SBPs is also spreading in Spain and Italy and
177 starting to expand to South America ([AFJ 2010](#)).

178 **2.2 Experiment preparation and design**

179 The study was prepared in a randomized block design (RBD) using 10 control and 10 biochar-
180 amended plots (3×3m plot size), allocated to five blocks, each treatment being replicated within
181 each block. Biochar was incorporated in the top 20 cm to a concentration of 4% (w/w), based on
182 a preliminary sustainability screening that identified this biochar's maximum loading capacity
183 ([Verheijen et al., 2019](#)) as the compromise between that leading to maximal benefits on soil water
184 retention and nutrient exchange for the studied soil, and minimal trade-offs on other traditional
185 soil health indicators (e.g. pH, enzymatic activity, plant germination and growth, earthworm
186 preference/avoidance behavior). In September 2022, the field site was rotovated by tractor. Soil
187 was removed from each plot to a depth of 20 cm and biochar was mixed homogeneously with the
188 soil by using a cement mixer before returning the soil/biochar mixture to each plot. Subsequently,
189 the whole field site, including the plots, was sown with a SBP seed mixture (Fertiprado[©]
190 company) containing two grasses (*Lolium multiflorum* and *L. perenne*) and seven legumes
191 (*Trifolium subterraneum*, *T. michelianum*, *T. resupinatum*, *T. vesiculosum*, *T. incarnatum*, *T.*
192 *repens*, and *Ornithopus sativus*). Even though *Trifolium repens* and *Lolium perenne* are not
193 biologically annual, summer drought restricts them to an annual life cycle. The seeding rate was
194 30 kg per ha, the standard rate used for SBP by farms in the region. However, two plots were not
195 properly sown by mistake (one control and one biochar-amended), thereby reducing the number
196 of usable replicates per treatment to 9 (in an unbalanced randomized block design). The pasture

197 was not grazed to maximize seedbank production and N₂ fixation by legumes, in accordance with
198 the SBP management practices during the establishment stage in the first season after seeding.

199 **2.3 Vegetation sampling and processing**

200 For sampling of SBP community composition, the first survey was conducted in January 2023
201 after the start of grass tillering. In this survey, we used 20×20 cm quadrats within each of the
202 plots, removed all plants from the quadrats, and sorted them to species level for biomass
203 weighing. For this phase of pasture development, it was the most feasible quadrat size to
204 maximize species capture, while retaining reasonable time and effort for separating plants. A
205 second survey was conducted in April 2023 at the peak of biomass development when pasture
206 was in the flowering phase. In this survey, we used 40×40cm quadrats, which proved to be most
207 feasible in this phase of pasture development, also to maximize species capture while having
208 reasonable time efficiency. Again, all plants were removed from the quadrats, sorted by species,
209 and we recorded individual count-based abundances of each species and biomass. All plants were
210 oven-dried for three days at 65°C before weighing. Thus, in the peak of biomass our data
211 consisted of both single-species dry biomass weights and abundances, as well as of species' vigor
212 (biomass of individuals of each species; dry biomass divided by abundance). Turboveg 2.0
213 software ([Henekens and Schaminée 2001](#)) was used to store species count-abundance data and
214 export the matrix combining all plots.

215 **2.5 Data analysis**

216 To analyze how biochar incorporation into the soil affects count-based total and relative
217 abundance, total seed mixture biomass and relative biomass, diversity metrics based on counts
218 and biomass (richness, Shannon-Weiner index, Gini-Simpson's index, and Pielou's evenness), as

219 well as Leaf Area Index (LAI), we used linear mixed effects (LME) models by restricted
220 maximum likelihood (REML) with bounded optimization by quadratic approximations (a.k.a.
221 bobyqa optimizers) in the R (R core team 2025; v 4.5.1) packages ‘lme4’ (Bates et al. 2015) and
222 ‘lmerTest’ (Kuznetsova et al. 2017). Here, block was considered as a random effect, and biomass,
223 counts, and diversity metrics as response variables of treatments (fixed effect). Due to high
224 heterogeneity of species growth and varying species occurrence (Appendix S2), for the analyses
225 of single-species responses (biomasses, counts, and vigor) to treatments, we used robust linear
226 mixed effects models from the ‘robustlmm’ package (Koller 2016). These models are based on
227 robust scoring estimators and do not require any assumptions except the possibility of parameter
228 estimation. All frequent species, occurring in a minimum of five plots (out of nine) within
229 treatments were analyzed. In these models, Huber k weights were retained at 1.345 as a
230 reasonable balance between robustness and efficiency. As this was a field experiment utilizing 18
231 plots in an unbalanced RBD, in which species development may be affected by various other
232 confounding factors (e.g. seedbank variation, germination efficiency, and annual plant life history
233 strategy) we avoided specific tunings of the models as the patterns in species responses were not
234 used to generalize across landscape levels, rather, only within the context of a RBD experiment.
235 Here, species-specific biomass, abundances, and vigor were modeled as response variables of
236 treatments as fixed and blocks as random effects. To interpret the species responses to treatments,
237 we used t-values, model-adjusted standardized mean differences (SMD; calculated as the
238 difference between estimated marginal means divided by the residual standard deviation from the
239 model), confidence intervals, and percentage changes between treatments based on estimated
240 marginal means. As ‘robustlmm’ package does not provide p-values for the models, for each
241 species we first ran LME models via REML with bobyqa approximations in ‘lme4’ package to
242 extract degrees of freedom and then used them to approximate p-values for species responses in

243 robust models. However, these p-values cannot be ‘exact’, so we used them as indicative, not as a
244 sole criterion for interpretation of the results (provided in Appendices).

245 To assess the diversity contrasts of the pasture community between control and biochar
246 treatment, we modeled Renyi diversity profiles with Hill numbers (Rényi 1961, Hill 1973). After
247 calculating raw Renyi values, we fitted them with LME models as responses to treatments
248 interacting with α -levels (treated as numeric values) by using natural splines from “splines”
249 package (Base R) with four degrees of freedom in fixed effects. In random effects we used
250 blocks, as well as random slopes (also with four degrees of freedom for spline term) and
251 intercepts for plots to account for the within-plot correlation inherent for α -levels profiling. This
252 model specification was shown to be the best by likelihood ratio tests and by inspection of
253 residual plots compared to model with only random intercept for plot, and to those containing
254 random intercepts and slopes but with smaller degrees of freedom for spline term. Type III sum
255 of squares Anova using Satterthwaite's approximation for denominator degrees of freedom was
256 then used to test the treatment effect on the diversity profiles of the pasture community. In data
257 processing “dplyr” (Wickham et al. 2023) and “tidyr” (Wickham et al. 2024) packages were used,
258 graphs were made using ‘ggplot2’ (Wickham 2016), ggeffects (Lüdecke et al. 2018), and ‘see’
259 (Lüdecke et al. 2021) packages, whereas estimated marginal means were extracted from the
260 models with ‘modelbased’ package (Makowski et al. 2020). Calculations of diversity metrics
261 were made in the ‘vegan’ package (Oksanen et al. 2023).

262 To analyze the multivariate response of community composition to treatments, we used
263 multivariate abundance models with Gaussian distribution on log-transformed biomass data,
264 fitted with multivariate linear model, and negative binomial distribution fitted with multivariate
265 generalized linear model for counts data, in the package ‘mvabund’ (Wang et al. 2012). To

266 pinpoint potential species causing the difference in community composition between treatments
267 (i.e. indicator species), we employed multiple univariate testing on the fitted multivariate
268 abundance models. For count-based abundance data, first we modeled the multivariate response
269 of species from native flora to treatments, in which we used total biomass and total counts of seed
270 mixture species interacting with treatments, to see if biochar and seed mixture species affected
271 the community composition of native species. Afterwards, for both biomass-based and count-
272 based community composition data, we modeled the multivariate response of the whole
273 community composition to treatments, as well as to a soil nutrient limitation gradient (pH_{KCl} ,
274 Al^{3+} , and K^{+} concentration in the topsoil of 20 cm depth), that was found to be the most
275 prominent in the studied acidic hard-setting soil, influencing competitive dynamics of grasses and
276 forbs on a functional group level, by re-using data for these parameters from [Jelinčić et al, 2025](#).
277 As all the three parameters were well linearly related to each other, thus, to avoid
278 multicollinearity in the model, they were wrapped into a principal component by PCA, and the
279 PC scores of the PC1 were used as a predictor variable, as it alone explained 92% of variance. In
280 both biomass-based and count-based community composition models, block was used as a fixed
281 factor. Full multivariate abundance models are available in the [Appendix S3](#), whereas all R
282 scripts used in this paper, as well as corresponding datasets, are available on GitHub
283 [<https://github.com/JelAntun>]

284 **3. Results**

285 **3.1 Responses of plant species**

286 *Plant species biomass at early-stage pasture development*

287 There was no effect of biochar treatment on total aboveground biomass of seed mixture species at
288 the early pasture development stage (January 2023; $t = 0.41$, $p = 0.69$), but the relative biomass
289 increased by 19% ($t = 2.99$, $p = 0.011$) (Figure 1a and 1c). Regarding individual species
290 responses (Appendix S4: Figure S1), no effect of biochar treatment was found on joint biomass
291 of seed mixture grasses *Lolium multiflorum* and *Lolium perenne*, nor on native grasses *Vulpia*
292 *bromoides* and *Agrostis* sp., but there was a 62% decrease in biomass of *Poa annua* ($t = -3.04$,
293 $SMD = 1.49$). The joint biomasses of hairy clovers (*Trifolium subterraneum* and *T. incarnatum*),
294 non-hairy clovers (*T. michelianum*, *T. resupinatum*, and *T. vesiculosum*), and *Ornithopus* sp. were
295 not affected by biochar treatment. Among native forbs, the only confident biomass decrease was
296 observed for *Plantago coronopus*, by 70% ($t = -3.51$, $SMD = 1.71$). Biomasses of *Cerastium*
297 *glomeratum* and *Aphanes* sp. were also reduced in biochar treatment (by 49% and 54%,
298 respectively), but their responses were less confident ($t = -1.88$, $SMD = 0.96$ and $t = -1.62$, SMD
299 $= 0.79$, respectively) compared to that of *P. coronopus*. The response of other native forbs to
300 biochar treatment was low or negligible.

301 Regarding relative biomass responses (Appendix S4: Figure S2), joint relative biomass of *L.*
302 *multiflorum* and *L. perenne* was 40% higher in biochar treatment than in control ($t = 2.18$, $SMD =$
303 1.05). Relative biomass of *Poa annua* was lower in biochar than in control by 54% ($t = -2.62$,
304 $SMD = 1.29$), whereas joint relative biomass of *Vulpia bromoides* and *Agrostis* sp. did not differ.
305 Differences in joint relative biomass responses of hairy clovers and that of non-hairy clovers
306 were non-significant between treatments, as well as that of *Ornithopus* sp. Only *P. coronopus* and
307 *Aphanes* sp. showed a strong response to biochar treatment, whose relative biomass decreased by
308 64% and 52%, ($t = -3.06$, $SMD = 1.49$ and $t = -1.60$, $SMD = 1.32$, respectively), and with a
309 moderate response *Cerastium glomeratum* with a 43% decrease ($t = -1.54$, $SMD = 0.78$). Relative

310 biomass responses to biochar treatment among other native forbs were low or negligible.

311 Comprehensive RLME models of species biomass responses are listed in [Appendix S5](#).

312 *Plant species biomass at peak pasture development*

313 Biochar treatment significantly increased the total aboveground biomass of sown seed mixture
314 species by 110%, i.e. from 2.91 to 6.12 t/ha ($t = 4.34$, $p = 0.000$), as well as relative seed mixture
315 biomass from 44% to 69% ($t = 3.28$, $p = 0.005$) (Fig. 1). Leaf area index (LAI) in biochar
316 treatment was 20% higher than that in control ($t = 2.46$, $p = 0.025$). Regarding the biomass of
317 individual seed mixture species (Fig. 2a and 2b), the highest positive responses were shown
318 among legumes, i.e. *Trifolium michelianum* with 216% increase ($t = 2.08$, SMD = 1.0) and *T.*
319 *repens* with 181% increase ($t = 2.04$, SMD = 1.95). *Trifolium vesiculosum*, *T. incarnatum*, and
320 *Ornithopus sativus* also showed a positive response, but with intermediate effect sizes, whereas
321 *T. subterraneum* was indifferent to biochar addition to soil. The highest positive response of
322 grasses to biochar addition was shown by both *L. multiflorum* with a 170% increase ($t = 3.23$,
323 SMD = 1.56) and *L. perenne* with a 136% increase ($t = 3.90$, SMD = 1.89). Among native
324 grasses, biochar addition reduced the biomass of *Vulpia bromoides* by 62% ($t = -2.65$, SMD =
325 1.34), but not those of *Agrostis* sp. ($t = -0.33$, SMD = 0.16) and *Poa annua* ($t = -0.77$, SMD =
326 0.37). Biochar treatment tended to reduce biomass of some forbs, however not significantly, with
327 much smaller effects compared to biomass increases of abovementioned grasses and legumes.
328 Comprehensive graphs and RLME models of species biomass responses are listed in [Appendix](#)
329 [S4: Figure S3](#) and [Appendix S6](#), respectively.

330 Relative seed mixture species' total biomass in biochar treatment was increased by 59% ($t = 3.28$,
331 $p = 0.0047$) (Figure 1d). For *L. multiflorum* and *L. perenne* (Figure 2c and 2d), the same response

332 to biochar treatment was found for relative biomass ($t > 2.2$, $SMD > 1.0$), with an increase in
333 biochar treatment of 110% and 60%, respectively. Relative biomass increases of *T. michelianum*
334 and *T. repens* were high in biochar treatments (118% and 108% respectively), but with a
335 substantially lower effect compared to their total biomass ($t = 1.55$, $SMD = 0.75$ and $t = 1.40$,
336 $SMD = 0.82$, respectively). Among native grasses, the relative biomass of *Vulpia bromoides*
337 decreased in biochar treatments by 74% ($t = -3.05$, $SMD = 1.52$), and that of *Poa annua* by 42%
338 ($t = -2.19$, $SMD = 1.08$), whereas that of *Agrostis* sp. decreased by 40%, but with lower effect
339 size ($t = -1.42$, $SMD = 0.70$). Among native forbs, the only strong decrease in relative biomass in
340 biochar treatment was observed for *Cerastium glomeratum*, with a decrease of 53% ($t = -2.57$,
341 $SMD = 1.25$). Relative biomass of *Spergula arvensis*, *Spergularia purpurea*, *Illecebrum*
342 *verticillatum*, *Polycarpon tetraphyllum* and *Aphanes* sp. somewhat decreased in biochar
343 treatment but with a substantially lower effect size ($t < -1.3 < -1.7$, $SMD > 0.7 < 0.89$). Relative
344 biomass responses of seed mixture legumes *T. subterraneum*, *T. resupinatum*, *T. vesiculosum*,
345 and *Ornithopus sativus*, as well as of native forbs *Juncus bufonius* and *Plantago coronopus* to
346 biochar addition were negligible. Graphs and RLME models for species relative biomass
347 responses are available in [Appendix S2: Figure S4](#) and [Appendix S6](#), respectively.

348 *Count-based abundances during peak biomass*

349 At the functional group level, biochar addition to soil decreased the total number of forb counts
350 by 51% ($t = -3.36$, $p < 0.01$), and had no significant effect on grass ($t = -1.4$, $p = 0.09$), legume (t
351 $= 1.4$, $p = 0.18$), and total seed mixture species counts ($t = 1.55$, $p = 0.14$) ([Appendix S4: Figure](#)
352 [S5](#) and [Appendix S7](#)).

353 At the species level (Fig 2e and 2f), the strongest response was observed for *T. incarnatum* ($t =$
354 2.39 , $SMD = 1.39$) and *Trifolium repens* ($t = 1.99$, $SMD = 1.05$), with increases of 93% and 98%,
355 respectively, and to a lesser extent for *Lolium multiflorum* (increase of 66%; $t = 1.87$, $SMD =$
356 0.90) and *T. resupinatum* (increase of 62%; $t = 1.66$, $SMD = 0.80$). Among forbs, biochar
357 treatment showed a confident decrease in *Plantago coronopus* ($t = -4.15$, $SMD = 2.0$), *Vulpia*
358 *bromoides* ($t = -3.31$, $SMD = 1.60$), *Polycarpon tetraphyllum* ($t = -2.56$, $SMD = 1.28$), and
359 *Cerastium glomeratum* ($t = -2.13$, $SMD = 1.03$), whose counts decreased by 61%, 75%, 67%, and
360 55%, respectively. In addition, *Aphanes* sp., *Poa annua*, *Illecebrum verticillatum*, *Spergularia*
361 *purpurea*, and *Juncus bufonius* showed decrease in counts to some extent, however with much
362 lower effect size than that of aforementioned species. Graphs and RLME models of count-based
363 abundance responses are available in Appendix S4: Figure S6 and Appendix S8.

364 In terms of relative count-based abundance (Fig 2g and 2h), biochar treatment increased joint
365 seed mixture species from 16% to 37% ($t = 3.78$, $p = 0.0023$). On individual species level,
366 biochar treatment exhibited a very strong positive effect on seed mixture legumes *T. repens*, *T.*
367 *incarnatum*, and *T. resupinatum*, with an increase of 231%, 187%, and 170%, respectively ($t \geq$
368 3.4 , $SMD \geq 1.80$), followed by *O. sativus* ($t = 2.27$, $SMD = 1.13$) and *T. michelianum* ($t = 2.07$,
369 $SMD = 1.0$) with an increase of 139% and 102%, respectively. Strong positive response was also
370 found in seed mixture grasses with *L. multiflorum* ($t = 2.99$, $SMD = 1.50$) and *L. perenne* ($t =$
371 2.50 , $SMD = 1.22$) showing an increase of 151% and 98%, respectively. Among native species,
372 the only notable decrease in relative counts due to biochar application was found in *Plantago*
373 *coronopus* ($t = -2.73$, $SMD = 1.32$) and *Vulpia bromoides* ($t = -2.43$, $SMD = 1.17$), by 44% and
374 59%, respectively. The responses of relative count-based abundances of other native species to
375 biochar treatment were weak (Appendix S4: Figure S7 and Appendix S8).

376 *Plant species vigor at peak of biomass development*

377 Regarding the vigor (dry biomass of an individual plant), biochar treatment had a positive effect
378 on most species (Fig. 1i and Fig. 1j), but with highly varying extent and effect size. Among seed
379 mixture grasses, for *L. perenne* the vigor increased by 57% ($t = 2.15$, $SMD = 1.05$), whereas the
380 vigor of *L. multiflorum* improved by 63% but with a slightly lower effect size ($t = 1.90$, $SMD =$
381 0.91). Among legumes, *T. michelianum* had the strongest response, with an increase in vigor of
382 97% ($t = 1.91$, $SMD = 0.94$). The vigor response of other legumes to biochar addition was mostly
383 positive but weak. Vigor of native species *Agrostis* sp. and *Juncus bufonius* showed a strongest
384 response to biochar treatments in terms of effect size, increasing by 59% ($t = 3.33$, $SMD = 1.68$)
385 and 96% ($t = 3.13$, $SMD = 2.11$), respectively, as well as that of *Plantago coronopus* with an
386 increase in vigor of 153% ($t = 2.11$, $SMD = 1.04$). Vigor response of other native species was
387 mostly positive but weak. Graphs and RLME models for species vigor are available in [Appendix](#)
388 [S4: Figure S8](#) and [Appendix S6](#).

389 **3.2 Plant diversity at peak of biomass development**

390 Count-based Renyi diversity profile (Fig. 3) showed a slight contrast in diversity curve shape
391 between control and biochar treatment, as captured by only marginal interaction between
392 treatment and spline term ($F = 2.39$, $p = 0.08$), while the overall effect of biochar treatment was
393 also marginal ($F = 3.43$, $p = 0.08$). Biomass-based Renyi diversity profile curves showed a
394 parallel trend but still with marginally significant interaction term ($F = 2.82$, $p = 0.046$), while the
395 overall biochar treatment effect was also marginal ($F = 3.82$, $p = 0.07$). Detailed model outputs
396 for Renyi diversity profiles are provided in [Appendix S9](#).

397 Considering individual diversity indices, there was a marginal but non-significant impact of
398 biochar treatment on species richness ($t = -1.88$, $p = 0.08$), where estimated marginal mean of
399 richness in control treatment was 28, and in that of biochar was 25 (Fig 4a). Shannon index did
400 not significantly differ between control (2.27) and biochar treatment (2.24) ($t = 1.06$, $p = 0.30$)
401 (Fig 4b). Gini-Simpson index was also non-significantly different between control (0.79) and
402 biochar treatment (0.85) ($t = 1.30$, $p = 0.22$) (Fig 4c). Pielou's evenness was slightly and
403 marginally higher in biochar treatment (0.76) than that in control (0.68), but non-significant ($t =$
404 1.813 , $p = 0.09$) (Fig 4d). Simpson and Shannon effective number of species were somewhat
405 higher in biochar treatment (Fig 4e and 4f), but non-significant. Full LME models for the
406 diversity metrics are available in [Appendix S10](#).

407 **3.3 Multivariate responses of pasture community composition to biochar-amended soil**

408 Regarding the species counts, the results of multivariate abundance models showed that there was
409 a statistically significant overall difference in native flora composition between control and
410 biochar treatment (LRT = 143, $p = 0.009$) (Table 2). However, multiple univariate testing of the
411 model only recognized *Vulpia bromoides* (LRT = 15.4, $p = 0.014$) and *Plantago coronopus* (LRT
412 = 15.3, $p = 0.014$) as indicator species for control, whereas links of all other species to control
413 and biochar treatment were highly non-significant. In addition, both seed mixture species total
414 counts and biomass alone had no effect on native flora composition, but there was a significant
415 interaction between them and treatments regarding how they affect native flora composition
416 (LRT = 83, $p = 0.022$ and LRT = 104, $p = 0.003$, respectively) (Table 2).

417 Regarding the whole count-based community composition (seed mixture species included), the
418 results of multivariate abundance models showed that there was a statistically significant overall

419 difference between the control and biochar treatment (LRT = 162, $p = 0.008$) (Table 2). Count-
420 based plant community composition was only marginally affected by $\text{pH}_{\text{KCl}}\text{-Al}^{3+}\text{-K}^{+}$ gradient
421 (LRT = 101, $p = 0.07$) (Table 2), and the interaction between treatment and $\text{pH}_{\text{KCl}}\text{-Al}^{3+}\text{-K}^{+}$
422 gradient was not significant (LRT = 78, $p = 0.15$). Biomass-based multivariate abundance model
423 also showed significant general effect of biochar treatment on community composition (LRT =
424 106, $p = 0.03$), and significant effect of $\text{pH}_{\text{KCl}}\text{-Al}^{3+}\text{-K}^{+}$ gradient (LRT = 137, $p = 0.003$), but not
425 their interaction (LRT = 82, $p = 0.311$). No significant indicator species was found on treatment
426 level in biomass-based community composition (Table 2). Full multivariate abundance models
427 (including multiple univariate testing on species level) are available in Appendix S3.

428 4. Discussion

429 Minimal differences in species biomass between treatments during January were expected.
430 During winter, the SBP was not yet water-limited, and the soil was not within the hard-setting
431 phase, which occurs only later in spring during drought (Jelinčić et al. 2025). Furthermore,
432 potential positive effects on growth coming from legume N_2 fixation are expected to occur only
433 later in spring, as they gain bigger biomass. Similarly, nutrient limitations are expected to become
434 more pronounced later during the growth stage, thus, direct positive effects of biochar on soil
435 nutrient status, such as release of K^{+} , becomes more important as plant growth progresses. The
436 relative biomass of seed mixture species was 19% higher in biochar than in the control because
437 the growth of the native forbs is slow during winter, and their biomass increases later in the
438 spring (Jelinčić et al. 2025)

439 At the peak of flowering and biomass development in April, biochar treatment increased the total
440 yield of seed mixture species by 110%. At the species level, there was no difference between

441 relative and total biomass general trends, as similar responses were found for all species between
442 these two parameters, indicating a proportional/uniform effect of biochar on ratio of species'
443 biomass in a community. However, the relative biomass of native species was lower in the
444 biochar treatment compared to that of the control not because of a significant decrease in their
445 total biomass (except in the case of the weed species *Vulpia bromoides*) but because of a strong
446 increase in total biomass of seed mixture species. Regarding individual seed mixture species, the
447 most pronounced positive response of total and relative biomass to biochar addition was observed
448 for the grasses *Lolium multiflorum* and *L. perenne*, and for the legumes *Trifolium michelianum*
449 and *T. repens*, whereas other legumes showed a positive but weak response to biochar
450 application. Biochar application decreased both total and relative biomass of *Vulpia bromoides*,
451 which is likely due to competition from *Lolium* sp. (Dowling et al. 2004), who possesses
452 competitive traits such as rapid growth and extensive root system (Matzrafi et al. 2021), enabling
453 competitive advantage over less vigorous species such as *Vulpia* sp. Its reduction in biomass is
454 favorable, as *V. bromoides* is a weed species in pastures that decreases productivity and is not
455 very palatable (Weller et al. 2019). *Agrostis* sp., however, seemed to be resistant to this
456 competition effect, as its total biomass was not significantly different between treatments. The
457 slight effect of competitive exclusion coming from seed mixture species on native forbs in
458 biochar treatment was present during the peak biomass, as their biomasses were slightly reduced,
459 however these reductions were either insignificant or with a low effect size to be considered
460 harmful in the context of community stability. This trend of biochar positively affecting total and
461 relative biomass of seed mixture species and slightly reducing total biomass of some native forbs
462 can be expected, as the higher vegetation density in biochar treatment reduced light availability to
463 some extent (DeMalach et al. 2016, Tan et al. 2025, Hautier et al. 2009), and most of the native

464 forbs from this study were small therophytes growing in the lowest layers of the vegetation
465 canopy, thus struggling to reach adequate light levels.

466 A similar uniform effect of biochar on the ratios of species in a community was also apparent for
467 count-based total and relative abundances, in which *L. multiflorum*, *L. perenne*, *T. resupinatum*,
468 and *T. incarnatum* were the most abundant seed mixture species in biochar treatment. However,
469 considering relative abundances, the positive effect of biochar on seed mixture species was very
470 large, increasing their relative abundance from 100% to over 200%. This indicates that the
471 biochar treatment facilitated stronger establishment of seed mixture species compared to that of
472 the control soil in the early vegetation period, possibly by means of the previously observed
473 positive effects on germination for *Lolium* sp. (de la Rosa et al. 2014), and specifically for
474 legumes due to its positive effect on soil K⁺ concentration (Table 1), which benefits bacterial root
475 nodulation, thus increasing N₂ fixation capacity (Oram et al. 2014). Compared to this effect, the
476 slight decrease in the relative abundance of native species was notable only for *V. bromoides* and
477 *P. coronopus*, but their reduction was small compared to the very large increase in seed mixture
478 species abundance. The total count-based abundance of frequent native forbs mostly showed
479 around 50% or somewhat greater decrease in biochar treatment, in which the effect was also
480 strongest for *V. bromoides* and *P. coronopus*, followed by *Cerastium glomeratum*, *Polycarpon*
481 *tetraphyllum*, *Aphanes* sp. and *Poa annua*. This indicated a slight competition of seed mixture
482 species with native forbs in an early vegetation period, in which seed mixture species gained
483 competitive advantage by populating the available soil niches, considering the low competitive
484 ability of the mentioned forbs, as they were subordinate therophytes. However, since the
485 reduction of native forb abundances and their biomass in percentage terms was much lower
486 compared to that of an increase in some seed mixture species, this suggested that, in the biochar

487 treatment, simultaneous processes of i) soil resource-niche expansion for seed mixture species
488 and ii) slight competitive exclusion towards native forb species, were at play. Regardless, this
489 competitive exclusion was not strong, and it likely happened via light reduction by denser
490 vegetation canopy and higher biomass in biochar treatment as also indicated by higher LAI
491 ([Appendix S6](#)), while the soil niche expansion that maximized abundances of seed mixture
492 species was very high, which is good from both the agronomic and ecological perspectives. This
493 can also be seen by looking at the plant vigor results ([Figures 1i and 1j](#)), which indicated that,
494 despite native forb species having fewer total counts in biochar treatment ([Figures 1e-1h](#)), their
495 individual biomasses tended to increase, indicating higher vigor under competitive pressure in a
496 denser canopy. This indicated that in the biochar treatment interspecific thinning was at play in
497 affecting native forbs, conceptually similar to self-thinning rule or density-dependent mortality in
498 monoculture stands ([Westoby 1984](#), [Weiner 1988](#)). This was most pronounced in *Plantago*
499 *coronopus*, which had the strongest reduction in total and relative count-based abundance in
500 biochar treatment, but with an increase in vigor of more than 150%. On the other hand, the
501 biomass and count-based abundances of *Juncus bufonius* and *Agrostis* sp. were only moderately
502 decreased in biochar treatment, but still their vigor was significantly increased, thus fulfilling
503 their vigor potential in biochar treatment with no negative effect on their population.

504 These results demonstrate that productivity of SBP in a natural granitic acidic soil (i.e., the
505 control) was below its ecological capacity. However, the biochar-induced increase in
506 aboveground productivity pushed the SBP community towards competitive exclusion of native
507 forbs by the seed mixture species, but without displacing them, thus competitive exclusion at play
508 only being moderate, allowing for the competitive coexistence between native forbs and seed
509 mixture species of a high agronomic value. This can be seen as there was no competitive

510 exclusion due to biochar-induced increase in SBP productivity between grasses and legumes
511 from the seed mixture, as is often the case, especially between ryegrasses and clovers under N
512 fertilization (Martin and Field 1984, Elgersma et al. 2020). Rather, the biomass and abundances
513 of species from both functional groups simultaneously tended to increase in biochar treatment,
514 confirming that the control soil was below its ecological capacity in terms of resources for their
515 growth, and biochar treatment increasing their populations without competition between them,
516 thus not compromising their niche partitioning. Therefore, seed mixture grass and legume species
517 seemed to be in a state of stable coexistence even under increased productivity in the experiment
518 presented here.

519 The results of diversity metrics support the above-mentioned findings, as biochar treatment
520 showed no noticeable negative effects on plant diversity of SBP neither for biomass-based nor for
521 count-based community composition. Marginally non-significant reduction in estimated mean
522 richness from control to biochar treatment was only from 28 to 25 species, respectively. Count-
523 based diversity indices that put weight on evenness in their diversity estimation were even
524 slightly higher in biochar treatment, even though still non-significant. Overall, considering the
525 count-based Renyi diversity profiles, biochar seemed to have a slight positive effect on the
526 evenness of species in a SBP community, without any either positive or negative ecological
527 consequence observed in this study. This occurred due to a moderate reduction in naturally
528 abundant forbs and increase in seed mixture species abundance, thus re-leveling their ratios, even
529 though the interaction between treatment and splines term did not appear significant, and the
530 overall diversity was only marginally affected by biochar treatment. When N fertilizers – mineral
531 or organic - are used as a yield-increasing measure in grasslands, their negative impact on species
532 evenness is expected due to an increase in abundance of few competitive plants, mostly grasses

533 (Liu et al. 2018). In our case, under biochar-induced increased grass and total seed mixture
534 species biomass, no significant differences in evenness were found; even a marginal slight
535 increase in count-based species evenness occurred, regardless the fact that biochar-amended soil
536 is expected to have a higher C/N ratio due to high SOM content, for which the case is usually the
537 opposite (Ma 2005). However, this does not imply that from a functional perspective the true
538 count-based diversity changed due to biochar application; it just captured the above-mentioned
539 trade-off in count-based abundances between seed mixture species and native forb species under
540 increased productivity, whose abundances became slightly more equal in biochar treatment (i.e.
541 seed mixture species abundances increased and those of native forbs moderately
542 decreased). Biomass-based Renyi diversity profiles, which are most direct means for assessing
543 yield-diversity trade-off, showed parallel trends between control and biochar treatment, while the
544 overall diversity differences between treatments were only marginal, highlighting resilience of
545 pasture community diversity under increased yield-driven competition from seed mixture species
546 of high agronomic value in biochar treatment.

547 Both biomass-based and count-based multivariate SBP community composition response to
548 treatments showed a statistically significant general difference, but only *Vulpia bromoides* and
549 *Plantago coronopus* were identified as indicator species for control, with no species identified for
550 the biochar treatment in count-based abundance models, while in biomass-based abundance
551 models, no species was significantly related to control or biochar treatment. Multivariate
552 abundance models can be sensitive even to subtle changes in community composition (Warton et
553 al. 2012), thus, the general differences detected in abundance models reflected the moderate
554 competitive exclusion observed in biochar treatment. However, as univariate testing showed no
555 clear separation by indicator species, and there was no species displacement due to competition in

556 biochar treatment, the observed differences in the SBP community between the two treatments
557 had no negative ecological consequence on a community level. They just reflected the increased
558 productivity with a simultaneous slight effect of competitive exclusion from seed mixture species
559 on native forbs, but without any drastic effects on community structure. In addition, the nutrient
560 limitation gradient prominent for the studied soil ($\text{pH}_{\text{KCL}} - \text{Al}^{3+} - \text{K}^+$ gradient) to some extent also
561 affected the variation of biomass-based community composition, indicating that the SBP
562 community composition was not a sole fixed consequence of biochar addition, but also slightly of
563 nutrient limitation. Simultaneous increase in soil pH and K^+ concentration and decrease in Al^{3+}
564 concentration is beneficial for SBP productivity; and in this acidic soil being one of requirements
565 for sustaining productivity. This shows that biochar addition significantly improved soil nutrient
566 status from the agronomic perspective with minimal effects on abundance of native grassland
567 species. As well, when considering the multivariate response of count-based native flora to seed
568 mixture total biomass and abundances, there were no statistically significant relationships, except
569 in the way seed mixture abundance interaction with treatments affected the native flora, reflecting
570 the previously discussed abundance changes due to moderate competitive exclusion between seed
571 mixture species and native forbs in biochar treatment.

572 ***Practical implications, limitations, recommendations***

573 The use of biochar as both a yield-increasing agronomic measure and a sustainable soil
574 management practice to improve ecosystem services also has potential from an ecological
575 management perspective in acidic drought-affected granitic soils. From our study it can be
576 concluded that biochar's positive effects on pasture productivity occurred without negative
577 effects on community composition and diversity. As biochar addition to the acidic hard-setting
578 soil increases pH in KCl only from 4.2 to 4.6, pH in H_2O from 5.1 to 5.65, and moisture content

579 for 32% in the root zone (0-20 cm) (Table 1), it indicates that increased productivity did not
580 compromise community structure as biochar operates via non-chronic multifaceted effects on soil
581 physico-chemical properties, instead of affecting only one either physical or chemical property.
582 For example, when lime is used to improve the soil pH of acidic soils in Iberian grasslands, the
583 target values are usually around 6-6.5, and the small increase in pH observed in our case would
584 even be considered insufficient for improving soil pH in standard agronomic practices, even
585 though this slight increase had a substantial effect on reducing nutrient limitation and improving
586 pasture productivity. The same reasoning can be applied to nutrients, in which biochar increased
587 K^+ concentration by 24%, but did not significantly affect Ca^{2+} , while even decreasing Mg^{2+}
588 concentration (but not below the sufficiency threshold), but it indirectly improved potential Ca
589 and Mg uptake for plants by decreasing the ratio of Al^{3+} to Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} (Table 1).

590 It seems that its multifaceted steady positive effects on multiple soil properties can highly
591 improve SBP productivity by increasing yield and abundance of seed mixture species of high
592 palatability, without pushing the native species in the pasture community towards competitive
593 displacement, thus, not compromising community composition and diversity. The limitation of
594 this study is that it took observations from only one vegetation season. However, this is in
595 accordance with a specific nature of SBP management, as the first season is used for pasture
596 establishment to maximize productivity, N_2 fixation by legumes, and seedbank production.

597 Regardless, for future research we recommend including permanent plots, as well as natural
598 grazing as another factor, to comprehensively understand biochar's effect on trade-offs between
599 yield and diversity in Mediterranean pastures on drought-affected soils. Another methodological
600 limitation is the small quadrat size (20 x 20 cm for early stage and 40 x 40 cm for peak biomass
601 stage) to survey pasture composition. However, due to high diversity and complex structure of

602 SBP's, these are the only suitable quadrat sizes to reasonably balance time-efforts with
603 experimental rigor, due to fast growth in spring and short time-window for surveys during peak
604 biomass before senescence.

605 **5. Conclusions**

606 i) Biochar-induced increase in pasture aboveground productivity did not cause negative trade-offs
607 with community composition and diversity

608 ii) Seed mixture grasses and legumes of high agronomic importance improved their biomass,
609 counts, and vigor in biochar treatment without compromising their niche partitioning

610 iii) There was a moderate competitive exclusion of native forbs by grasses and legumes, but
611 without reaching a competitive displacement, thus allowing for a competitive co-existence

612 iv) Due to higher productivity in the biochar treatment, native forbs responded to increased
613 competition by moderate reduction in counts, but increasing their vigor

614 v) As biochar's increase in yield and abundance of seed mixture species of high agronomic
615 importance occurred via balanced improvement of multiple soil properties, rather than
616 aggressively targeting a single property, our study demonstrates that biochar addition to soil has
617 the potential to maintain biodiverse pastures while providing substantial fodder productivity and
618 quality.

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622 **Data availability**

623 All R scripts used in this paper, as well as corresponding datasets, are available on GitHub

624 [<https://github.com/JelAntun>]

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639 Study conceptualization, statistical analyses, draft preparation: A.J.; field research: A.J., M.J.,

640 L.S.; editing, reviewing: A.C.B, F.V., O.G.P, S.J., P.S., T.D.; supervision, funding: A.C.B. and

641 F.V.

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643 **References**

- 644 Aarssen, L. W., and R. Turkington. 1985. "Biotic Specialization Between Neighbouring
645 Genotypes in *Lolium perenne* and *Trifolium repens* from a Permanent Pasture." *Journal of*
646 *Ecology*: 605–614.
- 647 AFJ. 2010. "David Crespo Takes C3 Pastures; the Next Step to Boost Soil Carbon." *Australian*
648 *Farm Journal*, April 1, 44–47.
- 649 Annex I of Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the Conservation of Natural
650 Habitats and of Wild Fauna and Flora. OJ L 206, 22.7.1992, 7.
- 651 Bai, Y., J. Wu, C. M. Clark, S. Naeem, Q. Pan, J. Huang, ... X. Han. 2010. "Tradeoffs and
652 Thresholds in the Effects of Nitrogen Addition on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning:
653 Evidence from Inner Mongolia Grasslands." *Global Change Biology* 16 (1): 358–372.
- 654 Bates, D., M. Mächler, B. Bolker, and S. Walker. 2015. "Fitting Linear Mixed-Effects Models
655 Using lme4." *Journal of Statistical Software* 67 (1): 1–48. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v067.i01>.
- 656 Bijay-Singh, and E. Craswell. 2021. "Fertilizers and Nitrate Pollution of Surface and Ground
657 Water: An Increasingly Pervasive Global Problem." *SN Applied Sciences* 3: 518.
658 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-021-04521-8>.
- 659 Biliias, F., D. D. Sewu, S. H. Woo, I. Anastopoulos, F. Verheijen, J. Lehmann, ... D. Kalderis.
660 2024. "Glossary of Terms Used in Biochar Research (IUPAC Technical Report)." *Pure and*
661 *Applied Chemistry* 96 (11): 1541–1572.
- 662 Cramer, W., J. Guiot, M. Fader, J. Garrabou, J. P. Gattuso, A. Iglesias, ... E. Xoplaki. 2018.
663 "Climate Change and Interconnected Risks to Sustainable Development in the Mediterranean."
664 *Nature Climate Change* 8 (11): 972–980.
- 665 Daniells, I. G. 2012. "Hardsetting Soils: A Review." *Soil Research* 50 (5): 349–359.
- 666 de la Rosa, J. M., M. Paneque, A. Z. Miller, and H. Knicker. 2014. "Relating Physical and
667 Chemical Properties of Four Different Biochars and Their Application Rate to Biomass
668 Production of *Lolium perenne* on a Calcic Cambisol During a Pot Experiment of 79 Days."
669 *Science of the Total Environment* 499: 175–184.
- 670 de Oliveira Ramos, P. P. 2011. *Water Balance and Soil Losses in Pastures*. Master thesis,
671 Instituto Superior Técnico, University of Lisbon, Portugal.
- 672 DeMalach, N., E. Zaady, and R. Kadmon. 2017. "Light Asymmetry Explains the Effect of
673 Nutrient Enrichment on Grassland Diversity." *Ecology Letters* 20 (1): 60–69.

674 Douglas, D. J., J. Waldinger, Z. Buckmire, K. Gibb, J. P. Medina, L. Sutcliffe, ... N. Koper.
675 2023. "A Global Review Identifies Agriculture as the Main Threat to Declining Grassland Birds."
676 *Ibis* 165 (4): 1107–1128.

677 Dowling, P. M., A. R. Leys, B. Verbeek, G. D. Millar, D. Lemerle, and H. I. Nicol. 2004. "Effect
678 of Annual Pasture Composition, Plant Density, Soil Fertility and Drought on *Vulpia*
679 *bromoides* (L.) SF Gray)." *Australian Journal of Agricultural Research* 55 (10): 1097–1107.

680 Edeh, I. G., O. Mašek, and W. Buss. 2020. "A Meta-Analysis on Biochar's Effects on Soil Water
681 Properties – New Insights and Future Research Challenges." *Science of the Total Environment*
682 714: 136857.

683 Elgersma, A., H. Schlepers, and M. Nassiri. 2000. "Interactions Between Perennial Ryegrass
684 (*Lolium perenne* L.) and White Clover (*Trifolium repens* L.) Under Contrasting Nitrogen
685 Availability: Productivity, Seasonal Patterns of Species Composition, N₂ Fixation, N Transfer
686 and N Recovery." *Plant and Soil* 221: 281–299.

687 European Commission. 2020. *EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030: Bringing Nature Back into Our*
688 *Lives*. COM(2020)380 final. Brussels.

689 European Commission. 2021. *EU Pollinator Initiative*. In *EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030:*
690 *Bringing Nature Back into Our Lives*. Brussels.

691 European Parliament and Council of the European Union. 2021. "Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 of
692 the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 Establishing the CAP Strategic
693 Plan." *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 435: 1–36.

694 Eurostat. 2024. "Utilised Agricultural Area by Categories in 2022." Accessed October 3, 2024.
695 <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tag00025>.

696 Gholamahmadi, B., S. Jeffery, O. Gonzalez-Pelayo, S. A. Prats, A. C. Bastos, J. J. Keizer, and F.
697 G. Verheijen. 2023. "Biochar Impacts on Runoff and Soil Erosion by Water: A Systematic
698 Global Scale Meta-Analysis." *Science of the Total Environment* 871: 161860.

699 Gholamahmadi, B., O. G. Pelayo, S. Isaka, I. Campos, M. Martins, A. C. Bastos, ... F. G.
700 Verheijen. 2025. "The Impact of Biochar Application on Sponge Function, Water Erosion, and
701 Vegetation Cover in a Mediterranean Vineyard Soil." *Journal of Environmental Management*
702 388: 125916.

703 Hejzman, M., P. Hejzmanova, V. Pavlů, and J. Beneš. 2013. "Origin and History of Grasslands in
704 Central Europe – A Review." *Grass and Forage Science* 68 (3): 345–363.

705 Gui, X., X. Xu, Z. Zhang, L. Hu, W. Huang, L. Zhao, and X. Cao. 2025. "Biochar-Amended Soil
706 Can Further Sorb Atmospheric CO₂ for More Carbon Sequestration." *Communications Earth &*
707 *Environment* 6 (1): 5.

708 Hautier, Yann, Pascal A. Niklaus, and Andy Hector. "Competition for light causes plant
709 biodiversity loss after eutrophication." *Science* 324, no. 5927 (2009): 636-638.

710 Hennekens, S. M., and J. H. Schaminée. 2001. "TURBOVEG, a Comprehensive Database
711 Management System for Vegetation Data." *Journal of Vegetation Science* 12 (4): 589–591.

712 Hernández, G., O. Valdés-López, M. Ramírez, N. Goffard, G. Weiller, R. Aparicio-Fabre, ... C.
713 P. Vance. 2009. "Global Changes in the Transcript and Metabolic Profiles During Symbiotic
714 Nitrogen Fixation in Phosphorus-Stressed Common Bean Plants." *Plant Physiology* 151 (3):
715 1221–1238.

716 Hernández-Esteban, A., M. L. López-Díaz, Y. Cáceres, and G. Moreno. 2019. "Are Sown
717 Legume-Rich Pastures Effective Allies for the Profitability and Sustainability of Mediterranean
718 Dehesas?" *Agroforestry Systems* 93: 2047–2065.

719 Hill, Mark O. 1973. "Diversity and Evenness: A Unifying Notation and Its Consequences."
720 *Ecology* 54 (2): 427–432. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1934352>.

721 Humbert, J. Y., J. M. Dwyer, A. Andrey, and R. Arlettaz. 2016. "Impacts of Nitrogen Addition
722 on Plant Biodiversity in Mountain Grasslands Depend on Dose, Application Duration and
723 Climate: A Systematic Review." *Global Change Biology* 22 (1): 110–120.

724 IUSS (International Union of Soil Sciences). 2014. *World Reference Base for Soil Resources*
725 *2014: International Soil Classification System for Naming Soils and Creating Legends for Soil*
726 *Maps*. World Soil Resources Reports No. 106. Rome: FAO.

727 Jeffery, S., F. G. Verheijen, D. Abalos, and A. C. Bastos. 2024. "Plant Productivity with Biochar
728 Applications to Soils." In *Biochar for Environmental Management*, 331–352. Routledge.

729 Jeffery, S., D. Abalos, M. Prodana, A. C. Bastos, J. W. Van Groenigen, B. A. Hungate, and F.
730 Verheijen. 2017. "Biochar Boosts Tropical but Not Temperate Crop Yields." *Environmental*
731 *Research Letters* 12 (5): 053001.

732 Jelinčić, A., L. B. Simões, M. Jongen, F. G. A. Verheijen, O. Gonzalez-Pelayo, P. Silva, S.
733 Jeffery, T. Domingos, and A. C. Bastos. 2025. "Biochar Application to Soil Alleviates Nutrient
734 Limitation, Drought Stress, and Soil Hardness, While Improving Aboveground Productivity in a
735 Mediterranean Sown Pasture." Research Square. Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-8575938/v1>

737 Jongen, M., A. C. Bastos, A. Jelinčić, L. Simões, O. Gonzalez Pelayo, J. Niemeyer, et al. 2024.
738 "Biochar, Plant Productivity and Community Structure: A Two-Year Study in a Newly Sown
739 Legume-Rich Pasture in Portugal under Ambient and Reduced Precipitation." *SSRN Electronic*
740 *Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5215014>.

741 Kidd, J., P. Manning, J. Simkin, S. Peacock, and E. Stockdale. 2017. "Impacts of 120 Years of
742 Fertilizer Addition on a Temperate Grassland Ecosystem." *PLoS ONE* 12 (3): e0174632.

743 Klein, N., C. Theux, R. Arlettaz, A. Jacot, and J. N. Pradervand. 2020. "Modeling the Effects of
744 Grassland Management Intensity on Biodiversity." *Ecology and Evolution* 10 (23): 13518–13529.

745 Koller, M. 2016. "robustlmm: An R Package for Robust Estimation of Linear Mixed-Effects
746 Models." *Journal of Statistical Software* 75 (1): 1–24.

747 Kuznetsova, A., P. B. Brockhoff, and R. H. B. Christensen. 2017. "lmerTest Package: Tests in
748 Linear Mixed Effects Models." *Journal of Statistical Software* 82 (13).

749 Leuschner, C., S. Lott, A. Schmitz, J. Wellinohoff, M. Komainda, and J. Isselstein. 2024. "Plant
750 Species Richness in Intensively Managed Temperate Wet Grasslands: Current State and the
751 Importance of Edge Habitats." *Biodiversity and Conservation*: 1–20.

752 Liu, J., Y. Cui, X. Li, B. J. Wilsey, F. Isbell, S. Wan, ... D. Wang. 2018. "Reversal of Nitrogen-
753 Induced Species Diversity Declines Mediated by Change in Dominant Grass and Litter."
754 *Oecologia* 188: 921–929.

755 Lüdecke D (2018). "ggeffects: Tidy Data Frames of Marginal Effects from Regression Models."
756 *Journal of Open Source Software*, 3(26), 772. doi:10.21105/joss.00772.

757 Lüdecke, D., I. Patil, M. S. Ben-Shachar, B. M. Wiernik, P. Waggoner, and D. Makowski. 2021.
758 "see: An R Package for Visualizing Statistical Models." *Journal of Open Source Software* 6 (64):
759 3393.

760 Ma, M. 2005. "Species Richness vs Evenness: Independent Relationship and Different Responses
761 to Edaphic Factors." *Oikos* 111 (1): 192–198.

762 Makowski, D., M. Ben-Shachar, I. Patil, and D. Lüdecke. 2020. "Estimation of Model-Based
763 Predictions, Contrasts and Means." CRAN. <https://github.com/easystats/modelbased>.

764 Martin, M. P. L. D., and R. J. Field. 1984. "The Nature of Competition Between Perennial
765 Ryegrass and White Clover." *Grass and Forage Science* 39 (3): 247–253.

766 Mauchamp, L., A. Mouly, P. M. Badot, and F. Gillet. 2016. "Impact of Nitrogen Inputs on
767 Multiple Facets of Plant Biodiversity in Mountain Grasslands: Does Nutrient Source Matter?"
768 *Applied Vegetation Science* 19 (2): 206–217.

769 Matzrafi, Maor, Christopher Preston, and Caio Augusto Brunharo. "evolutionary drivers of
770 agricultural adaptation in *Lolium* spp." *Pest Management Science* 77, no. 5 (2021): 2209-2218.

771 Meng, Z., X. Mo, W. Meng, B. Hu, H. Li, J. Liu, ... M. He. 2023. "Biochar May Alter Plant
772 Communities When Remediating the Cadmium-Contaminated Soil in the Saline-Alkaline
773 Wetland." *Science of the Total Environment* 899: 165677.

774 Mosquera-Losada, M. R., S. Rodríguez-Barreira, M. L. López-Díaz, E. Fernández-Núñez, and A.
775 Rigueiro-Rodríguez. 2009. "Biodiversity and Silvopastoral System Use Change in Very Acid
776 Soils." *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 131 (3–4): 315–324.

777 Müller, I. B., C. Buhk, M. Alt, M. H. Entling, and J. Schirmel. 2016. "Plant Functional Shifts in
778 Central European Grassland Under Traditional Flood Irrigation." *Applied Vegetation Science* 19
779 (1): 122–131.

780 Oksanen, J., G. Simpson, F. Blanchet, R. Kindt, P. Legendre, P. Minchin, ... J. Weedon. 2023.
781 *vegan: Community Ecology Package*. R package version 2.6-6.1. [https://CRAN.R-](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan)
782 [project.org/package=vegan](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan).

783 Orford, K. A., P. J. Murray, I. P. Vaughan, and J. Memmott. 2016. "Modest Enhancements to
784 Conventional Grassland Diversity Improve the Provision of Pollination Services." *Journal of*
785 *Applied Ecology* 53 (3): 906–915.

786 Pallett, D. W., O. L. Pescott, and S. M. Schäfer. 2016. "Changes in Plant Species Richness and
787 Productivity in Response to Decreased Nitrogen Inputs in Grassland in Southern England."
788 *Ecological Indicators* 68: 73–81.

789 Petermann, J. S., and O. Y. Buzhdygan. 2021. "Grassland Biodiversity." *Current Biology* 31 (19):
790 R1195–R1201.

791 Plantureux, S., A. Peeters, and D. McCracken. 2005. "Biodiversity in Intensive Grasslands:
792 Effect of Management, Improvement and Challenges." *Agronomy Research* 3 (2): 153–164.

793 R Core Team 2025. R: "A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing." R Foundation
794 for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <<https://www.R-project.org/>>.

795 Rényi, Alfréd. 1961. "On Measures of Information and Entropy." In Proceedings of the Fourth
796 Berkeley Symposium on Mathematical Statistics and Probability, vol. 1, 547–561. Berkeley:
797 University of California Press.

798 Rochon, J. J., C. J. Doyle, J. M. Greef, A. Hopkins, G. Molle, M. Sitzia, ... C. J. Smith. 2004.
799 "Grazing Legumes in Europe: A Review of Their Status, Management, Benefits, Research Needs
800 and Future Prospects." *Grass and Forage Science* 59 (3): 197–214.

801 Serviço de Reconhecimento e de Ordenamento Agrário. 1970. *Cartas dos Solos de Portugal*. I
802 Volume, 6a Edicao, Setembro de 1970.

803 Spiegelberger, T., C. Deléglise, S. DeDanieli, and C. Bernard-Brunet. 2010. "Resilience of Acid
804 Subalpine Grassland to Short-Term Liming and Fertilisation." *Agriculture, Ecosystems &*
805 *Environment* 137 (1–2): 158–162.

- 806 Srivastav, A. L., N. Patel, L. Rani, et al. 2024. "Sustainable Options for Fertilizer Management in
807 Agriculture to Prevent Water Contamination: A Review." *Environmental Development and*
808 *Sustainability* 26: 8303–8327.
- 809 Tan, Tianyuan, Huamei Xia, Cong He, Yao Wei, Xiang Liu, Zhenhua Zhang, Jin-Sheng He, and
810 Lin Jiang. "Trait-Mediated Competition for Light Underpins Plant Diversity Loss Under
811 Eutrophication." *Global Change Biology* 31, no. 9 (2025): e70521.
- 812 Teixeira, R. F. M., T. Domingos, A. P. S. V. Costa, R. Oliveira, L. Farropas, F. Calouro, ... J. P.
813 B. G. Carneiro. 2011. "Soil Organic Matter Dynamics in Portuguese Natural and Sown Rainfed
814 Grasslands." *Ecological Modelling* 222 (4): 993–1001.
- 815 Teixeira, R. F., V. Proenca, D. Crespo, T. Valada, and T. Domingos. 2015. "A Conceptual
816 Framework for the Analysis of Engineered Biodiverse Pastures." *Ecological Engineering* 77: 85–
817 97.
- 818 Tilman, D. 1982. *Resource Competition and Community Structure*. No. 17. Princeton, NJ:
819 Princeton University Press.
- 820 Tsiafouli, M. A., E. Thébault, S. P. Sgardelis, P. C. De Ruiter, W. H. Van Der Putten, K.
821 Birkhofer, ... K. Hedlund. 2015. "Intensive Agriculture Reduces Soil Biodiversity Across
822 Europe." *Global Change Biology* 21 (2): 973–985.
- 823 USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service. 2014. *Soil Survey Staff. Soil Taxonomy: A Basic*
824 *System of Soil Classification for Making and Interpreting Soil Surveys*, 3rd ed. USDA Handbook
825 436.
- 826 van de Voorde, T. F., T. M. Bezemer, J. W. Van Groenigen, S. Jeffery, and L. Mommer. 2014.
827 "Soil Biochar Amendment in a Nature Restoration Area: Effects on Plant Productivity and
828 Community Composition." *Ecological Applications* 24 (5): 1167–1177.
- 829 Verheijen, F. G., A. C. Bastos, H. P. Schmidt, and S. Jeffery. 2019. "Biochar and Certification."
830 In *Sustainability Certification Schemes in the Agricultural and Natural Resource Sectors*, 113–
831 136. Routledge.
- 832 Wang, X., W. L. Zheng, H. M. Yuan, M. van Kleunen, F. H. Yu, and M. H. Li. 2024. "Biochar
833 Produced from Diverse Invasive Species Improves Remediation of Cadmium-Contaminated
834 Soils." *Biological Invasions*: 1–12.
- 835 Wang, Y. I., U. Naumann, S. T. Wright, and D. I. Warton. 2012. "mvabund – An R Package for
836 Model-Based Analysis of Multivariate Abundance Data." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 3
837 (3): 471–474.
- 838 Wang, Z., M. He, X. Lu, Z. Meng, J. Liu, and X. Mo. 2024. "Biochar Addition Can Negatively
839 Affect Plant Community Performance When Altering Soil Properties in Saline-Alkali Wetlands."
840 *Frontiers in Plant Science* 15: 1347658.

841 Warton, D. I., S. T. Wright, and Y. Wang. 2012. "Distance-Based Multivariate Analyses
842 Confound Location and Dispersion Effects." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 3 (1): 89–101.

843 Weiner, J. A. C. O. B. 1988. "The influence of competition on plant reproduction." *Plant*
844 *reproductive ecology: patterns and strategies*: 228-245.

845 Weller, S., S. Florentine, B. S. Chauhan, A. Mahmood, and A. Florentine. 2019. "Effects of
846 Various Ecological Factors on the Germination of Two Crop and Pasture Weed Species, *Vulpia*
847 *bromoides* and *Vulpia myuros*." *New Zealand Plant Protection* 72: 135–146.

848 Westoby, M. 1984. "The Self-Thinning Rule." In *Advances in Ecological Research*, Vol. 14,
849 167–225. Academic Press.

850 Wickham, H. 2016. *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. New York: Springer-Verlag.
851 <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>.

852 Wickham, H., R. François, L. Henry, K. Müller, and D. Vaughan. 2023. "dplyr: A Grammar of
853 Data Manipulation". R package version 1.1.4. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.dplyr>

854 Wickham, H., François, R., Henry, L., Müller, K., and Vaughan, D. 2024. "dplyr: A Grammar of
855 Data Manipulation". R package version 1.1.4. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.package.dplyr>

856 Yuan, H. M., W. Xue, S. Roiloa, J. Yao, and F. H. Yu. 2024. "Increasing Biochar Diversity
857 Promotes the Impacts of Plant Diversity on Remediating Cadmium in Soil." *Journal of Plant*
858 *Ecology* 17 (6): rtae068

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867 **Tables**

868 Table 1. Averages of soil chemical properties and moisture content in control and biochar
 869 treatments (adapted from Jelinčić et al. 2025, under review)

Soil property	Control	Biochar
Soil organic matter %	3.09	4.96
Total N (g kg ⁻¹)	1.42	2.18 ⁸⁷¹
P _i (mg kg ⁻¹)	16.61	16.67
K ⁺ (mg kg ⁻¹)	136	168
Ca ²⁺ (mg kg ⁻¹)	657	598 ⁸⁷²
Mg ²⁺ (mg kg ⁻¹)	117	82
pH H ₂ O	5.07	5.65 ⁸⁷³
pH KCl	4.17	4.57
Al ³⁺ (mg kg ⁻¹)	31.29	9.14 ⁸⁷⁴
Ca ²⁺ /Al ³⁺	24	96
Mg ²⁺ /Al ³⁺	4	13 ⁸⁷⁵
Mn ²⁺ (mg kg ⁻¹)	73.16	39.85
Average soil moisture % (Feb-Apr 2023)	14.80	19.55 ⁸⁷⁶

877 P_i and K⁺ represent inorganic P and K contents calculated from P₂O₅ and K₂O, respectively.

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884 Table 2. Results of multivariate ANOVA's fitted on multivariate abundance models for pasture
 885 community composition responses to treatments, seed mixture species, and soil nutrient
 886 limitation

Native flora response to:	Res. df.	Df.diff.	LRT	P
Treatment	16	1	143.5	0.009
Seed mixture counts	15	1	50.9	0.412
Seed mixture biomass	13	1	50.8	0.424
Block	10	4	384.6	0.005
Treatment * seed mixture counts	9	1	83.3	0.023
Treatment * seed mixture biomass	8	1	104.2	0.003
The whole count-based community response to:				890
Treatment	16	1	162.4	0.008
Nutrient limitation	15	1	102.3	0.069
Block	11	4	372.5	0.022
Nutrient limitation * treatment	10	1	78.3	0.147
The whole biomass-based community response to:				894
Treatment	16	1	106.5	0.030
Nutrient limitation	15	1	136.8	0.035
Block	11	4	83.7	0.092
Nutrient limitation * treatment	10	1	81.8	0.311

898 Res.df. – residual degrees of freedom, Df. diff. – difference in degrees of freedom, LRT –
 899 likelihood ratio test statistic, P – p-values of multivariate ANOVA's, Nutrient limitation - soil
 900 pH_{KCl}-Al³⁺-K⁺ gradient